

ASSESSMENT OF SPUTUM SAMPLES FOR *Streptococcus pneumoniae* IN UMTH
MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Streptococcus Pneumoniae causes life- threatening disease of the respiratory tract. It is the most important of all the tropical disease in terms of morbidity and mortality. Across-sectional study on relationship between *Streptococcus pneumonia* and age was carried out at General Out-patient Department (G.O.P.D) of University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH) Borno State, Nigeria. Variables assessed were sputum sample for *S. pneumoniae*, Age (No. of years), sex (male and female). A total of 211 patients were surveyed comprising 118(55.9%) male and 93(44.10%) female, 122(57.8%) of the study population were adult and 89(42.2%) adolescent. One hundred and thirty (61.6%) of the patient had *S.pneumoniae* infection in their sputum. *S. pneumoniae* infection of these 74(35.1%) were males while 56(26.5%) were female but the difference was not found to be statistically significant ($P>0.05$) infection rate was higher among the adult 82(38.8%), than the adolescence 48(22.8%) and the difference was found to be statistically significant ($P<0.005$). however, Antibiotics sensitivity pattern of *streptococcus pneumonial* to some antibiotics indicated total resistance of sample as 0(0.0). penicillin, 28(21.5%) ciprofloxin, 22(16.9) streptomycin, 20(15.4%) erythromycin, 15(11.5) Rifampin, 15(11.5%) Gentamycin, 12(9.2%) Norfloxacin and 18(13.8%) Lincocin respectively. The antibiotic sensitivity profile in this study goes a long way to describe the degree of abuse and misuse of common routine antibiotics in the study area. Thus the information in this study is helpful in knowing the final solution of indiscriminate use of antibiotic and checking out to formulate the control strategy in future.

KEYWORDS: Assessment, sputum samples, *Streptococcus pneumonia*, UMTH, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Pneumonia is a disease of the lung that is caused by a variety of bacteria including streptococcus, staphylococcus, pseudomonas, mycoplasma and several viruses. The disease may be divided into two forms, bronchial pneumonia which is most prevalent in infants, young children and lobar pneumonia which is more prone to occur in younger adults. A majority (more than 80%) of the cases of lobar pneumonia are caused by streptococcus pneumonia.

The prevalence of streptococcus pneumonia resistant in the tropical Africa, South African including the study area is penicillin- resistant strains are increasing. An association between HIV infection and Streptococcus pneumonia resistant to penicillin and tetracycline has been reported by Paul *et al* (1994) - protection is good against deep pneumococcal infections (especially septicemia and meningitis). Immunization is suggested for those at highest risk of infection including those 65 years or older and generally should be a single lifetime dose. Streptococcus pneumoniae, and conjunctivitis. Severe infections can occur in the elderly and those already in poor health or immune-suppressed. Risk of infection is increased following planectomy (Gilks *et al.*, 1997).

In tropical and developing countries, streptococcus pneumoniae is a major pathogen, responsible for acute life-threatening pneumonia and bacteria in those co-infected with HIV. It is also a common cause of childhood pneumonia and serious infections in patients with sickle cell disease incidence of streptococcus pneumonia infections among patient attending tuberculosis clinics in Ekpoma (Musher *et al.*, 1997), Nigeria in the it is note that age group 1-9 years was mostly affected by streptococcus pneumonia and that children had the highest incidence of both streptococcus pneumoniae and that children had the highest incidence of both streptococcus pneumonia and mycobacterium tuberculosis followed by farmers (Paul and Kimari, 1994). A high incidence of

pneumococcal bacteria usually occur in infants under 2 years of age, low in teenagers and young adults and high in people above 60 years when immunity is low due to age (Peterson, 2006).

Treatment is usually with Beta-lactam antibiotics. In the 1960s, nearly all strains of streptococcus pneumonia were the susceptible to penicillin, but since that time, there has been an increasing prevalence of resistance, especially in areas of high antibiotic use (Ryan *et al.*, 2004). An amoxicillin and clavulanic acid combination (co-amoxiclav/Augmetin) is often used to treat otitis media (Tleyeh *et al.*, 2006). The incidence of penicillin

resistant streptococcus pneumonia (pneumococcus) has risen steadily worldwide and now complicates diagnostic and treatment strategies for infections due to this organism (Taiwo, 2004).

Aims – This is to assess sputum samples of patients attending (G.OPD) of UMTH for streptococcus pneumoniae and to determine its antibiotic sensitivity profile which may help tremendously in describing the degree of abuse and misuse of common routine antibiotics in the study area.

METHODS

Study Area

A study was carried out in GOPD (General Out-patient Dept of UMTH), University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital Borno State, Nigeria.

Sampling Method

Every patient of age (one year and above) that was brought to the consulting room was eligible to be part of the study. Two hundred and eleven patients were enrolled during the survey period and subject to the patient's consent and agreement. A patient was given clean dry wide necked, leak proof container to cough deeply to produce a sputum-specimen. Where as in children mucopus aspirated from the nasopharynx of the patient. The sample were examined in a biological safety cabinet, the specimen was cultured in blood agar and incubated aerobically. However, chocolate agar was incubated in a carbon dioxide enriched candle jar for 37°C over night. After the blood and chocolate agar cultures were examined, significant growth of streptococcus pneumonia identified and confirmed by optochia disc sensitivity method. Which is the ideal confirmatory biochemical test of *S. pneumoniae*, pneumoniae are sensitive to optochia (ethylhydrocupreine hydrochloride), when impregnated with 5µg of optochia and placed on a primary sputum culture and the plate incubated aerobically. Subsequently, a rapid presumptive identification was done to determine the zone of inhibition of at least 10mm.

Staining Procedure

The samples (sputum) were stained as described by Sir Hans Christian Gram staining procedure to distinguish between gram positive and gram negative organisms.

Subsequently, a thick smear was made on a clean grease free slide allowed to air dry and fixed by gentle flaming over a Bunsen burner flame.

The dried smear was stained and further treated with Lugol's iodine for 30 seconds, (i.e. mordant). The smear was then washed with water and decolorized with 95% alcohol with continued application until no more colour appears to flow from the preparation and finally washed off using buffered distilled water.

The smear was counter stained with neutral red (or safranin) for 1-2 minutes. The slide was washed with distilled water and allowed to air dry and was examined under oil immersion objective lens (x100) of a light microscope. (Gram positive appears purple and while negative appears pinkish).

Antibiotic Sensitivity Test (Disc Method)

The isolated organism from the sputum sample (*S. pneumoniae*) were evenly spread into a plate of chocolate agar with a standard wire loop. The multi-disc impregnated with antibacterial agents were removed aseptically and placed at the centre of the medium using a sterile forceps and pressed evenly.

The disc was gently picked and applied on the surface of the agar plate with flamed forceps to avoid interference of external organism or to prevent contamination by external organism. The plate placed in a candle jar and was incubated at 37°C for 18-24hrs after which the sensitivity pattern was read.

Data Analysis

Data assessable were analyzed using PEPI, the computer programme for epidemiological students association was established using chi square test at 95% confidence limit.

RESULTS

Result of the 211 patients' studied 118 (55.9%) were males and 93(44.1%) were female as shown in table 1. Majority of the adult with 122 (57.8%) were between 14 to 70 years while 89 (42.2%). Adolescents, there was how however no statistical difference between ages ($X^2= 0.60$, $df = 0.44$).

Table 2 shows the Assessment of sputum for *S. pneumonia* infection by age and sex. A total of 211 patient's sputum samples were examined for *S. pneumoniae*, 130(1.6%) were infected while 81(38.4%) were negative of the 89 adolescent examined. 48(22.8%) had *S. pneumoniae* in their sputum while 82(38.8%) of 122 adults were infected. Infection rate was higher among the adolescent than in adults and the difference was found to be statistically significant ($X^2=3.84$, $df =1$, $P=0.05$). Of the 118 males examined, 74(35.1%) were infected while the corresponding figure for female infected was 56(26.5%) out of 93. Although more males than females were *S. pneumoniae* positive, the difference were not found to be statistically significant ($X^2=0.14$, $df=1$, $P= 0.71$).

The antibiotic (drugs) sensitivity pattern of positive *S. pneumoniae* samples show at 0(0.0) of samples were sensitive to penicillin, 28(21.5%) were sensitive to Ciprofloxacin, 22(16.9) were sensitive to Streptomycin, 20(15.4%) were sensitive to Erythromycin, 15(11.5%) were sensitive to Rifampin, 15(11.5) were sensitive to Gentamycin, 12(9.2) were sensitive to Norfloxacin and 18(13.8%) were sensitive to Lincocin respectively.

DISCUSSION

The prevalence of streptococcus pneumonia observed in this study was 61.6%. The high prevalence of streptococcus pneumoniae could be attributable to increasing resistance and tolerance to penicillin in geographical location of Borno State, and Tropical countries. Gilks (1997).

The prevalence of streptococcus pneumonia infection was statistically higher among adult than adolescent, which suggests that age is an important factor in the aectiology of streptococcus pneumonia among the studied population. This agrees with highest incidence of streptococcus pneumonia among patients attending clinic in Ekpoma, Nigeria (Egwu *et al* (2006).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion the study showed a strong correlation between age and *S. pneumoniae* infection. A high incidence of pneumonococcal bacteria is usually low in teenagers and young adults and high in older people when immunity is low due to age. The information in this study is helpful in knowing the final solution to *S. pneumoniae* infection in Borno State and checking out to formulate the prevention strategy in future.

Table 1: Age and sex distribution of study population

Age (In years)	Male		Female		Both sexes	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
1 – 14yrs	47	(23.3)	42	(19.9)	89	(42.2)
14 – 70yrs	71	(33.6)	51	(24.2)	122	(57.8)
Total	118	(55.9)	93	(44.1)	211	(100.0)

Table 2: Assessment of sputum for *S. pneumonia* by Age and sex distribution of study population

Age (In years)	Male		Female		Both sexes	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
1 – 14yrs	48	(22.8)	41	(19.4)	89	(42.2)
14 – 70yrs	82	(38.8)	40	(19.0)	122	(57.8)
Total	130	(61.6)	81	(38.4)	211	(100.0)

Table 3: Drugs (Antibiotic) sensitivity pattern of streptococcus pneumonia to some antibiotics

Sensitivity		
Antibiotics	No.	%
Penicillin	0	(0.0)
Ciprofloxacin	28	(21.5)
Streptomycin	22	(16.9)
Erythromycin	20	(15.9)
Rifampin	15	(11.5)
Gentamycin	15	(11.5)
Norfloxacan	12	(9.2)
Lincocin	18	(13.8)
Total	130	(100.0)

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